

Synthesis of 8,8'-(polymethylene-*o*-xylyl-dioxy)di(pyrano[4,3-*b*]-1-benzopyran-10*H*-10-one) and its conversion to corresponding diacrolein derivative

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Abstract : 6,6'-Tethered-di(4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-carboxaldehyde) undergoes inverse electron demand [4+2] cycloaddition reaction with ethoxyethene to produce *endo*-di(pyrano[4,3-*b*]-1-benzopyran), which produces diacrolein when treated with NaOMe in methanol.

Keywords : 3-Formylchromone, benzopyran, Diels-Alder reaction.

Introduction

Most of the dichromones appeared in the literature are pharmaceutically important¹. Disodium cromoglycate (1) acts as an antiasthmatic and antiallergic compound, its binding activity to human serum albumin was determined². A khellin like 7,7'-glycerol-briged dichromone 2 exhibits antianaphylactic activity. In passive cutaneous anaphylaxis testing, compound 2 was found to be more effective at low dose than 1³. Dichromones isolated from *Selaginella delicatula* exhibit antitumor activity⁴.

the synthesis of 6,6'-(polymethylenedioxy)di(chromone-3-carbaldehyde)⁷. In continuation to our interest in synthesising various dichromones⁸, we report herein the synthesis of di(pyrano[4,3-*b*]-1-benzopyran) and its decomposition⁹ to diacrolein.

Results and discussion

A solution of 3 in dichloromethane was heated under reflux for 20 h in the presence of excess ethyl vinyl ether (EVE). Solvent and excess EVE was distilled out from

Fig. 1

Chromone-3-carbaldehyde, which is a very good building block for the synthesis of chromone-linked or chromone-fused heterocycles, exhibited itself also as a heterodiene. It undergoes [4+2] cycloaddition by inverse electron demand with activated olefin ethoxyethene⁵ to produce pyrano[4,3-*b*]-1-benzopyran moiety, which has structural resemblance with fungal metabolite fulvic acid⁶. Presence of OH, OMe or OAc group at 6-position of 3-formylchromone exhibited higher *endo*-selectivity in the above cycloaddition reactions. We have earlier reported

the reaction mixture. The concentrate yielded 4 in moderate yields (Scheme 1).

The structure of the compound was established on the basis of IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral analysis. Although chromone-3-carbaldehyde produced a mixture of *exo* and *endo* diastereomers with the later as the predominant product⁵, in the case of di(chromone-3-carboxaldehyde) a single diastereomer was isolated. The two possible diastereomers 4-*endo* and 4-*exo* are shown in Fig. 2.

Scheme 1

Fig. 2

To distinguish these two isomers, coupling of C₃-H deserves special attention. In the *endo*-isomer, C₃-H enjoys an axial-axial and an axial-equatorial coupling with H_X and H_Y at C-4 respectively, whereas, in the *exo*-isomer, corresponding C₃-H enjoys equatorial-axial and equatorial-equatorial coupling. ¹H NMR spectral analysis of **4** shows C₃-H at δ ~5.2 appears as double doublet with *J*-values 9.9 and 1-1.5 Hz, which claims an axial-axial coupling, i.e. C₃-H is at axial position. So, compound **4**, which was isolated from the reaction mixture is an *endo*-isomer. Previous result⁵ corroborates this observation.

Formation of *endo*-isomer is further supported by the presence of alkoxy group at 6 and 6'-position in **3**⁵. The same reaction was extended with **3c**, which was synthesised by Vilsmeier-Haack reaction of **8**. Compound **8** was obtained from the reaction of **6** and **7** (Scheme 2).

Compound **4** was then treated with NaOMe in MeOH to yield **5** in good yield (Scheme 1). The structure of compound **5** was established on the basis of IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral analysis. Formation of **5** may be rationalised as follows : MeO⁻ attacks at the C-1 position of **4** to generate **9**, which forms **10** by the expulsion of the OEt group. Base induced pyran ring opening of **10** (→**11**) followed by ring closure with the departure of OMe group leads to **5** (Scheme 3).

In conclusion, we have achieved a synthesis of di(pyrano[4,3-*b*]-1-benzopyran-10*H*-10-one) and its conversion to corresponding diacetaldehyde, which may be a potent synthon for the synthesis of various diheterocycles and other interesting macrocyclic compounds.

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

Experimental

The recorded melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Beckman IR 20A, NMR spectra on a Bruker 300 MHz spectrometer and mass spectra on a Qtof micro YA 263 instrument, and elemental analysis on a Perkin-Elmer 240c elemental analyser.

Synthesis of 6,6'-tethered-di(chromone-3-carbaldehyde) 3 :

Compounds **3a** and **3b** were synthesised following the literature procedure^{7,8c}.

Synthesis of 3c :

POCl₃ (2 ml, 22 mmol) was injected in dry DMF (2 ml, 26 mmol) under argon atmosphere at 0–5 °C temperature and allowed to stir under this condition for 5 min. A solution of **8** (406 mg, 1 mmol) in dry DMF (10 ml) was injected slowly at that temperature. After complete addition, the resultant reaction mixture was stirred under cold condition for 10 min and then allowed to stir at room temperature for 6 h. The resultant thick reddish reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice (100 g) when a yellow coloured solid appeared. It was filtered, washed with water, dried in air and recrystallised from dichloromethane to afford a light yellow solid **3c** in 60% yield.

3c : Yield 290 mg (60%); m.p. 238–240 °C (Found : C, 69.55; H, 3.65. C₂₈H₁₈O₈ requires : C, 69.71; H, 3.76%); ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 3085, 1690, 1648, 1638, 1478, 1317; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) : 5.30 (4H, s, 2 × OCH₂), 7.39 (2H, dd, *J* 9.0, 3.0 Hz, 2 × H-7), 7.42–7.45 (2H, m, ArH), 7.48

(2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, 2 × H-8), 7.52–7.57 (2H, m, ArH), 7.72 (2H, d, *J* 3.0 Hz, 2 × H-5), 8.52 (2H, s, 2 × H-2), 10.38 (2H, s, 2 × CHO).

*Synthesis of 8,8'-tethered-di{3,4-dihydro-4aH-pyrano[4,3-*b*]-1-benzopyran-10H-10-one} 4 :*

To a solution of **3** (1 mmol) in dichloromethane (100 ml) excess EVE (2 ml, 20 mmol) was added and the resultant mixture was heated under reflux for 20 h by circulating cold water through the reflux condenser. On concentration the reaction mixture produced a solid, which was filtered out and crystallised from chloroform to afford **4a-c** in moderate yields.

4a : Yield 300 mg (53%); m.p. 168–170 °C (Found : C, 65.85; H, 5.63. C₃₁H₃₂O₁₀ requires : C, 65.95; H, 5.71%); ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 2933, 1667, 1603, 1484; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) : 1.29 (6H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, 2 × CH₃), 2.24 (2H, quintet, *J* 5.7 Hz, CH₂), 2.28–2.36 (2H, m, 2 × H_X), 2.56 (2H, ddd, *J* 12.7, 6.6, 1.0 Hz, 2 × H_Y), 3.62–3.73 (2H, m, 2 × H_A), 3.97–4.08 (2H, m, 2 × H_B), 4.15 (4H, t, *J* 5.7 Hz, 2 × OCH₂), 5.13 (2H, brt, *J* 8.0 Hz, 2 × H-4a), 5.19 (2H, dd, *J* 9.9, 1.0 Hz, 2 × H-3), 6.87 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, 2 × H-6), 7.05 (2H, dd, *J* 9.0, 2.7 Hz, 2 × H-7), 7.38 (2H, d, *J* 2.7 Hz, 2 × H-9), 7.56 (2H, s, 2 × H-1); ms : *m/z* 565 (M+H⁺), 587 (M+Na⁺).

4b : Yield 250 mg (42%); m.p. 176–178 °C (Found : C, 66.75; H, 5.98. C₃₃H₃₆O₁₀ requires : C, 66.88; H, 6.12%); ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 2920, 1680, 1615, 1460; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) : 1.29 (6H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz, 2 × CH₃), 1.63 (2H, quintet, *J* 6.3 Hz, CH₂), 1.82–1.87 (4H, m, 2 × CH₂), 2.25–2.36

(2H, m, 2 × H_X), 2.57 (2H, ddd, *J* 12.0, 5.1, 1.8 Hz, 2 × H_Y), 3.63–3.73 (2H, m, 2 × H_A), 3.97–4.08 [6H, m, 2 × (OCH₂ + H_B)], 5.13 (2H, brt, *J* 7.8 Hz, 2 × H-4a), 5.20 (2H, dd, *J* 9.9, 1.8 Hz, 2 × H-3), 6.88 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, 2 × H-6), 7.04 (2H, dd, *J* 9.0, 3.0 Hz, 2 × H-7), 7.34 (2H, d, *J* 3.0 Hz, 2 × H-9), 7.56 (2H, s, 2 × H-1).

4c : Yield 300 mg (48%); m.p. 220–222 °C (Found : C, 68.88; H, 5.36. C₃₆H₃₄O₁₀ requires : C, 69.00; H, 5.47%); ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) 2920, 1670, 1599, 1486; δ_H (CDCl₃) : 1.29 (6H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz, 2 × CH₃), 2.26–2.33 (2H, m, 2 × H_X), 2.51–2.65 (2H, m, 2 × H_Y), 3.61–3.75 (2H, m, 2 × H_A), 3.93–4.10 (2H, m, 2 × H_B), 5.10–5.31 (4H, m, 2 × H-4a + 2 × H-3), 5.16 (4H, s, 2 × OCH₂), 6.87 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 2 × H-6), 7.07 (2H, dd, *J* 8.4, 1.2 Hz, 2 × H-7), 7.37 (2H, d, *J* 1.2 Hz, 2 × H-9), 7.46–7.50 (4H, m, ArH), 7.55 (2H, s, 2 × H-1).

Treatment of 4 with NaOMe :

NaOMe was generated from sodium (12 mg, 0.5 mmol) and dry methanol (10 ml). To it compound 4 (0.25 mmol) was added and the resultant reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 3 h when a red coloured solution was obtained. Solvent from the reaction mixture was removed under reduced pressure. Ice-water (10 g) was added to the concentrate and the resultant mixture was acidified with dilute HCl. A faint yellow solid deposited, which was filtered out, washed with water, dried in air and recrystallised from CHCl₃ to afford 5 in good yield.

3,3'-[6,6'-{(α,ω-trimethylenedioxy)-di(4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-3-yl)}]diacrolein 5a :

Yield 80 mg (68%); m.p. 212–214 °C (Found C, 68.52; H, 4.18. C₂₇H₂₀O₈ requires : C, 68.64; H, 4.27%); ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) 2949, 2839, 1676, 1643, 1475; δ_H (CDCl₃) : 2.37 (2H, quintet, *J* 6.0 Hz, CH₂), 4.30 (4H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz, 2 × OCH₂), 7.28–7.35 [6H, m, 2 × (2ArH + vinylic H)], 7.45 (2H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz, 2 × vinylic H), 7.65 (2H, d, *J* 2.7 Hz, 2 × H-5), 8.22 (2H, s, 2 × H-2), 9.67 (2H, d, *J* 6.3 Hz, 2 × CHO).

3,3'-[6,6'-{(α,ω-pentamethylenedioxy)-di(4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-3-yl)}]diacrolein 5b :

Yield 75 mg (60%); m.p. 242–244 °C (Found : C, 69.43; H, 4.76. C₂₉H₂₄O₈ requires : C, 69.59; H, 4.83%); ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) 2980, 2815, 1670, 1645, 1460; δ_H (CDCl₃) :

1.70–1.73 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.91–1.96 (4H, m, 2 × CH₂), 4.12 (4H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz, 2 × OCH₂), 7.32–7.36 (4H, m, 4 × vinylic H), 7.41–7.46 (4H, m, ArH), 7.62 (2H, d, *J* 2.7 Hz, 2 × H-5), 8.22 (2H, s, 2 × H-2), 9.68 (2H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, 2 × CHO).

3,3'-[6,6'-{(o-xylidloxy)-di(4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-3-yl)}]diacrolein 5c :

Yield 65 mg (49%); m.p. 254–256 °C (Found : C, 71.78; H, 4.02. C₃₂H₂₂O₈ requires : C, 71.91; H, 4.15%); ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) 3040, 2915, 2805, 1660, 1650, 1465; δ_H (CDCl₃) : 5.39 (4H, s, 2 × OCH₂), 7.28 (2H, dd, *J* 7.8, 7.5 Hz, 2 × vinylic H), 7.35–7.39 (2H, m, ArH), 7.49–7.57 (8H, m, ArH), 7.65–7.67 (2H, m, ArH), 8.89 (2H, s, 2 × H-2), 9.60 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, 2 × CHO); ms : *m/z* 535 (M+H⁺), 557 (M+Na⁺).

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